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ETHICAL COMPLIANCE IN RESEARCH PRACTICE AMONG POST GRADUATE STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR, NIGERIA.

Dr Delight O. Idika

&

Dr Richard A. Ojini

Department of Educational Foundations, University of Calabar
Calabar

Abstract

The paper investigated ethical compliance in research practice of post graduate students in University of Calabar, Nigeria. Survey design was adopted. The population for the study consisted of 1713 post graduate students in the 13 faculties of the university, out of which 832 (517 males; 315 females, and 502 Masters; 330 Ph.D) representing the sample for the study was drawn through disproportionate stratified random sampling technique. A researcher developed instrument tagged "Post Graduate Students' Ethical Compliance Research Practice Questionnaire PGSECRPQ" was used in data collection. The instrument was divided into two parts. Part A elicited information on postgraduate students' demographic while B comprised 4 sub-units of 40 items measuring postgraduate students' ethical compliance in research practice. The instrument's reliability was obtained using the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient method that measured internal consistency and yielded an estimate which ranged from .71 to .88. Analysis of collected data was done with the use of population t-test, one-way-analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple analysis of variance (MANOVA). Based on the results, it was found that post graduate students in University of Calabar have not shown much ethical compliance in their research practice especially in psychometric properties of data collection instruments ($X=24.66 < \mu= 25.00$; $t = -1.26 < t= 1.98$), and data analysis ($X=23.26 < \mu 25.00$; $t= -6.39 < t=1.98$). Their exhibition of ethical compliance in data collection, reporting and the overall, was however, significantly high. The findings also showed significant difference in the ethical compliance among male and female students. In other words, the result indicated that the female students were less committed ($X=98.03$) than their male counterparts ($X= 101.40$) in the exhibition of ethical compliance. It was found too, that the post graduate students of different faculties differed significantly in exhibition of ethical compliance with respect to psychometric properties of instruments and data analysis (F-ratio =2.65 and F-ratio=2.42 at $P < .05$) while significant difference does not exist between them in data analysis and reporting (F-ratios=2.09 and F-ratio = 1.20 at $P > .05$) The mean values showed that Allied Medical Sciences showed a relatively high ethical compliance in their research practice, while faculty of Arts indicated the least commitment to ethical compliance on research practice. Among the recommendations made was the need to expose

students to orientation in ethical practice in research through resource persons organised by faculty of Education.

Key words: Ethical compliance, proper conduct, research practice, postgraduate students.

Introduction

Ethical compliance in research practice has become an issue on the front burner for education stakeholders and social researchers. Researchers are more than ever before concerned with discipline in employing and adhering to the most appropriate approach in the conduct of research. Hence, researchers are expected to strictly follow what are the barest minimum requirements for the integrity of any research they embark upon (Isangedighi, 2012). This observation supports the theory of consequentiality that posits that researchers weigh their actions to see whether the total good consequences outweigh the total bad consequences. If the total good consequences are greater, then, the action is morally proper and vice versa. It is therefore, advantageous that for every research, the investigator develops and follows appropriate code of conducts considering the need placed on research to accomplish critical goals, particularly those connected to national development.

In the course of research investigation, ethical compliance is reflected when a researcher ensures that the purpose and procedure for data collection are clearly communicated to whoever is concerned either as a participant or consumer. This is to eliminate any form of breach. Isangedighi further explains the stand of P. D. Reynolds on what a researcher who is ethical compliant should do. The researcher makes arrangement to provide feedback to anticipate who may request for it, respect and protect at all time the dignity, privacy and interest of the research participant; uses deception when it is absolutely necessary and consult other researchers when ethical dilemmas arise in research. An orientation of students towards the compliance to ethical code of research conduct connotes that the research students ought to be encouraged to maintain integrity in the research process in terms of psychometric properties of data collection instrument, data analysis and reporting among others. In short the American Psychological Association (APA) Code of Conduct (2002) outlined the responsibility of the researcher, informed consent, privacy and confidentiality as the four major issues that could show a researcher to be ethically compliant. It is important to note that research output from higher institutions of learning ought to be credible enough to exert the needed impact on development of the society.

Universities are known seat of meaningful research worldwide. Researches done in universities are carried out by the academic body comprising majorly the lecturers and the postgraduate students. The researches done by post graduate students contribute significantly to the development of individual, the institution and the community at large. Graduate researches are therefore, no less meaningful and reliable than those conducted by their mentoring teachers, especially if the proper conducts are observed in the process. Ethical issues are very important in research not only in the University of Calabar, but also in world class universities where students try to be smart by doing many fraudulent things in their research conduct. The Office of Research Integrity (2011) reported some of the matters of ethical concern to include plagiarism, misuse of privileged information, fabrication, falsification of research data and or results.

misrepresentation of credentials, in proposing, performing, or reviewing research, or in reporting research results. The Office defined the above as research misconducts and this excludes honest error or differences of opinion.

Generally, misconducts are viewed as a serious professional art that is subject to sanctions imposed by the University, professional associations and federal agency particularly if such agency is funding the research or has the particular research being proposed to it. As part of its effort to transform the quality of research emanating from the Institution, University of Calabar Graduate School has embarked on a number of programmes and has set up facilities and equipment aimed at promoting the production of post graduates with capacity for high quality policy relevant research (Bisong, 2012). Guidelines or Handbook for rules and regulations as it is named for these preparation exist for all registered students to help build integrity in the work to be able to qualify for Masters or Ph.D. These guidelines constantly undergo revisions and updates to reflect the need of the now. The anti-plagiarism device, 'Turn-it-in' has been put in place to check students' level of plagiarism in their work and build integrity in research. The turn-it-in software checks and confirms originality of students' theses such that only 10% level of plagiarism is allowed for any work coming into University of Calabar Graduate School. In order to further build in responsibility and quality in the conduct of graduate research in the institution, the School is currently designing to be mounted two-university wide courses; Communication/Writing Skill course and Research Methodology to help students address the detected key challenges concerned with planning and conduct of research and communication of research findings. It is believed that at the completion of programme of course, students will improve in research writing skills and cut down plagiarism and other related crime or misconduct in research (Personal Communication with the Dean of Graduate School, University of Calabar, 3rd July, 2017).

Enhancement of research skills of both students and all teachers of graduate programmes including supervisors are being vigorously pursued through Graduate theses workshops and seminars aimed further at improving the University's research quality. Every step taken in the proper conduct of graduate research involves a quality implication. In pursuance of integrity and quality, the University of Calabar Graduate School has been committed to equipping the School with standard Board, Theses defense and Seminar rooms having multimedia and communication system and a standard e-library with adequate computers, internet with wide bandwidth. Efforts and the gains of linking graduate research design and output to the needs of industry, governments and non-governmental agencies through synergy and partnership are also major reasons for the university graduate seminars meant to produce first class research students whose output in research can compete favourably at the global stage. Through seminars, greater awareness of possible implications of research misconducts is being created. The awareness of the danger and the lack of trust for fabricated data or result of research, of engaging research instruments without proper validation or test of reliability, intentional manipulations of statistical data and improper reporting among others are critical issues that not only University of Calabar is concerned with but all

other universities globally. The outcry on the use of materials without due acknowledgement and other forms of misconducts are observably the concern of many stakeholders of research today. And students as well as scholars involved in research practice are beginning to be aware that things are changing and they need to align their research conducts with global recognized best practice within research community.

This implies that the old practice when students presented verbal introduction to school heads and collect data from pupils or students in somewhat disorganized test condition, code and analyse data and present results has to change to a better practice where ethical compliance is made. The seeming complaints by students of refusal of some school heads or would be participants to respond to the instruments for data collection seem to confirm the doubts of some stakeholders of research that some things about researches done by our post graduate students are not proper; the inadequacy could point to the absence of ethical compliance before and during research practice and after data collection. A close examination of the research work of most post graduate students have tended to reveal a lot of manipulations and other actions which seem to reflect lack of integrity in the conduct of educational research. This misconduct has been particularly observed during data handling and reporting of research findings (Idika, 2016). A few common but dishonest practices such as filling the spaces left unfilled, recopying of responses onto fresh questionnaire, helping to fill the required number in the questionnaire to mention some, point to the probable lack of ethical behaviour. The theory of ethics called duty-based consequentiality theory tends to be relevant to this study. The theory posits that we determine our moral responsibility of an action by weighing the consequences of our action. Then we determine whether the total good consequences outweigh the total bad consequences. If the total good consequences are greater, then, the action is morally proper. If the bad consequences are greater, then, the action is morally improper. This theory posits that the end result of an action is the sole determining factor of its morality. From the foregoing, relating the proposition to the issue at hand, dishonest activities involved in the identified research practices such as determination of validity and reliability of the data collection instrument, data collection procedure, data analysis and reporting could lead to enormous results. Thus, the significance of this result (end) to the stakeholders would be biased hence, decision taken from this information will not be truthful and may lead to confusion. The consequence of biased research outcome may attribute very little or nothing to national development.

Hence, the need to orientate students to develop the character of honest research practice by ensuring compliance in the activities taken by them to get their theses and other research projects done. Developing these character traits would be a step in the right direction to fulfil the goal expectation of the national policy of education on tertiary education which is to contribute to national development through high level manpower training. In order to achieve the national goal, there is urgent need to institutionalize ethical compliance for students offering research courses. Various measures have been introduced to checkmate fraud and improve research integrity among students especially in University of Calabar through the combined effort of the Graduate School and the University's Directorate of Research and Quality Assurance.

However, with the rising methodological challenges and level of plagiarism still being detected, the situation leaves us in doubts as to the extent to which the post graduate students have been involved in strict research compliance practices. The

research compliance practice among post graduates identified in this study included determining psychometric properties of data collection instrument. For example, validity requires that items correspond with concept to be measured. Reliability concerns statistics analysis of a pilot test of the validated data collection instrument to determine its consistency in measuring what it purports to measure. A lot of lapses have been observed in results presented by some students in this regard.

The activity involving collection of data is another research practice in this study. This procedure is prone to manipulations as some students usually decide to manipulate data in a bid to avoid some of the obstacles involved in data collection and analysis (Idika, 2016).

Coming up with a good and validated instrument has been seen as a task too difficult to accomplish because the exercise demands time, commitment and scientific or technical know-how, all of which could cause many researchers to take alternatives including adapting or modifying to use existing instruments regardless of the implications (Nenty and Umoinyang, 2004). Such implications arising from inability of students to handle the process of determining instrument properties have resulted in failure of research to yield valid data for various psychological measurements (Joshua, 2005)

The skills of instruments construction and validation are among the least to be applied appropriately and efficiently in research practice (Ali, 2009; Idika, 2016). The researchers however, noted that specific studies on this subject matter are yet to be common in literature. In a study by Asim, Kalu and Ekwueme (2007) to determine the levels of practical skills displayed in unpublished science education post graduate theses of Faculty of Education, University of Calabar, and research reports in Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) Conference Proceedings, it was found that the application of the skills of instrumentation was marginally good. This implies that a number of students still exhibit some level of integrity in developing and carrying out proper determination of psychometric properties of their research instruments. This explains the need for a research like this to ascertain the extent to which post graduate students are involved in the maintenance of the ethical principles of research in the universities particularly University of Calabar.

Through literature and personal experiences, coupled with the result of the exploratory interview granted by the researchers, it was observed that students had issues regarding proper conduct of research with respect to data collection, analysis and reporting in higher magnitude than other practices involved in their process of research, hence, the need to further look through literature to buttress these observations. For instance, a number of concerned studies have identified this technique to be very critical but most challenging to researchers wishing to carryout empirical investigation: (Cohen, Manor & Morrison, 2011; Yee & Sam, 2012; Bakare & Bakare, 2014; Ayating & Uyanah, 2015; Eluwa and Eba, 2015, Umoinyang, 2015; Idika, 2016; Idika, Joshua & Umoinyang, 2017). In a study to investigate an analysis of problems encountered by post graduate students in Nigerian universities which tend to elongate their study period, Duze (2005) used a Postgraduate Students' Problem Questionnaire (PSPQ) to collect data from 48 respondents drawn using stratified random sampling from 15 federal – owned and 9 states – owned universities. The analysis of data revealed one of the findings of the study that showed data collection and analysis as a major problem; it does appear therefore, that in these activities, students do just anything; without following the

laid down ethics to collect data for their research.

On data collection and analysis, a good number of reviewed studies have reported inadequacy in these activities among graduate students particularly the female students. For instance, the study by Joshua, Nwogwugwu and Ikirima (2015) on data analysing skills via Scientific Package for Social Science (SPSS), sex was found to have a significant influence on research practices. A similar study on evaluation of the use and misuse of statistical techniques in educational research in university of Calabar was undertaken by Asim and Eni (2015). This study focused on graduate theses from six faculties. A random sample of 90 hypotheses from 30 theses was selected. The study captured the frequency of the use of different statistical techniques. Based on the assumptions underlying the use of some techniques, the researchers reviewed the appropriateness of the hypotheses of each thesis, the identified variables and the suggested statistical techniques. The evaluative study revealed gross research misconduct in the form of an abuse and misuse of statistical techniques for hypotheses testing among post graduate students in faculty of education, University of Calabar.

Writing research report comes in after completing the exercise of carrying out research, that is, relevant data had been collected and analysed appropriately. The review identified few empirical studies focusing on ethical issues on the reporting of research findings, and generally expressed concern that decision makers and practitioners are not only insufficiently informed by research but tend to be deceived by the twisted evidence that come with improper research practice. In a study to evaluate the conduct of research by post graduate students in Nigeria from the reporting perspective, Ali (2009) found the exhibition of compliance of this aspect of research practice to be significantly high. The calculated t-value of 81.0 was higher than the critical t-value of 1.97 at the .05 level of significance with degree of freedom of 209. This implied that the post graduate students properly applied their skills of reporting in the process of carrying out researches. Whether this is true among post graduate students of University of Calabar is a question to be answered.

In recent times, the findings of Bassey, Udida, Akwuegwu and Udey (2007) and Amadi, Ojini (2015) have also shown the research commitment of male postgraduates to be more than their female counterparts. On the other hand, Asim et al (2007) and Chen (2008) found difference in favour of the female. Incidentally, literature so far has revealed that the issue of difference in sex and ability in ethical compliance is still debatable. Therefore, the need to examine this variable in relation to research ethics of post graduate students is well informed.

In like vein, the link between the students' course of study (faculty) and exhibition of ethical compliance could be viewed from previous studies and could help to enhance students' ethical compliance in research. It is also a common belief that disciplines like science, management and social science, education, research and statistics could carry out research successfully without many difficulties than others, while in some quarters, contrary views are held which seem to differ with this idea. Amadi (2015) revealed significant difference in research practice of post graduate students of different areas of specialization. While Management science was the most favoured in Amadi's (2015) study; that of Eze (2011) which also revealed significant influence, showed that midwifery was more favourably disposed in their research skills than health information, nursing, and health technology which was the least.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine ethical compliance in research practice among post graduate students in university of Calabar. Specifically, the study sought to determine.

1. The extent of exhibition of ethical compliance by post graduate students in terms of establishing psychometric properties of data collection instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting
2. The sex differences among the post graduate students in terms of their ethical compliance in establishing psychometric properties of instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting
3. The faculty difference among the post graduate students in terms of their ethical compliance in establishing psychometric properties of instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting.

Hypotheses

1. The extent to which post graduate students in University of Calabar exhibit ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting is not significantly high.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female post graduate students in exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data collection, data analysis and reporting.
3. There is no significant difference among post graduate students in different faculties in their exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data collection, data analysis and reporting.

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for the study and was carried out at the University of Calabar, Cross River State. The researchers did not have to manipulate the variables but studied their outcomes in retrospect. University of Calabar is a 2nd Generation University being founded in 1975 in the south-south zone of Nigeria and is currently desiring a higher ranking and visibility in its research efforts. Hence, carrying out an indepth survey of her graduate students' compliance to proper research procedure could add to one of the ways to achieving such desires. The population for this study comprised all the post graduate students pursuing Masters' degree and Ph.D in University of Calabar. This number of students engaged in postgraduate courses in 2014/2015 and 2015/2016 sessions in all the 13 faculties of the university represented 1713. The choice of this group was based on the fact that they were currently undertaking research for their theses and had taken graduate seminar courses to have the experience being sought for by the researchers. The disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to select the subjects for this study. The stratification was based on sex and course of study/faculty.

The sample was 50% of faculties and 50% of population and the number so selected was 856 post graduate students (502 Masters; 330 Ph.D, and 517 males; 315 females) enrolled in 6 courses (Education, Social Sciences, Management Sciences, Arts, Sciences and Allied Medical Sciences). A questionnaire tagged "Post graduate students; Ethical Compliance Research Practice Questionnaire. (PGSECRPQ)" was used for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part: (A) sought

information about the students' demographic variables (sex, faculty/department, degree, year of study) while the second part (B) focused on the postgraduate students' ethical compliance in research practice. The ethical compliance scale consisted of 40 items that measured the level or extent of need of orientation of research practice ethics, on 4-point modified Likert scale: Very much orientation needed, much orientation needed, little orientation needed, No orientation needed. The use of 'orientation need' for compliance or noncompliance of graduate students with research ethical practice is justified by the desire to get honest and unbiased responses from the students. Therefore, the more orientation needed was an indication of less compliance by graduate students. To ensure construct validity of the scale, items were generated from prior exploratory interviews across groups of post graduate students during various interactions in formal and informal settings. Only items shared by over 50% of such students were included as items in PGSECRPQ.

The validity of the instrument was ascertained using the content validity approach in order to determine the extent to which the statements in the questionnaire correspond with the research objectives. The content validity was done through submitting the instrument to 3 experts in Research, Measurement and Evaluation who vetted and ascertained their adequacy for use in this research. The reliability was determined by the use of Cronbach Alpha Reliability method to get the internal consistency of the items making up the 4 sub-scales; this yielded reliability coefficient or estimate that ranged from 0.71 to 0.88. Ethical compliance of post graduate students was determined and adjudged significantly high by finding in each dimension the respondent or sample mean which must be greater than the reference or population mean. The respondent mean was calculated as the average of the 4 point scale used for data collection multiplied by 10 items of each sub-scale. That is, $4+3+2+1/4 = 2.5 \times 10 = 25$. In the case of the students' overall ethical compliance, the overall sample mean should be significantly greater than the reference mean score. That is, $2.5 \times 10 \text{ items} \times 4 \text{ sub-scales} = 100$.

Eight hundred and fifty six (856) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the selected sample through contact persons in the six different faculties with the help of 4 research assistance, post graduate students who are already conversant with the process of research. This was done over a period of one week. Out of this number, 10 were not returned and 14 were not completely filled. This gave a sample size of 832 and a return rate of 97.2%.

Results

Hypothesis one

Post graduate students' exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting is not significantly high.

The main variable in this hypothesis is the level of exhibition of ethical compliance in the four dimensions of research practice. The researcher reasoned that for a graduate student to be considered standard in his/her research practice in a particular dimension, he/she should score a minimum of 2.5/4 on each of the items in that dimension and therefore, 25 for the entire dimensions (each of the dimensions has 10 items, thus, $2.5 \times 10 = 25$). For the entire ethical compliance in research practice as a variable having four dimensions, the minimum score to depict standard research practice should be $2.5 \times 10 \times 4 = 100$.

The statistical analysis used to test this hypothesis was t-test for one sample mean, known as population t-test. The hypothesis was tested for each of the four dimensions of research practice and for the overall research practice. The result was presented on Table 1.

Table 1: Population T-Test Analysis of Ethical Compliance in Research Practice (N = 832)

S/No	variables	Reference mean score	Respondent mean score	SD	t-value	Sig
1	Psychometric properties of instrument	25.00	24.66	7.63	-1.26	.123
2	Data collection	25.00	26.26	7.23	5.03*	.000
3	Data analysis	25.00	23.26	7.83	-6.39*	.000
4	Reporting	25.00	25.93	7.24	3.70*	.000
5	Overall research practices	25.00	100.12	18.94	2.50*	.010

*significant at 0.05 level, critical t = 1.98, df = 830

The results presented on Table 1 showed that the two t-values and overall (5.03; 3.70) were each higher than the critical t-value of 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance with 830 degree of freedom except -1.26 and -6.39 respectively for psychometric properties of instruments and data analysis that showed negative t-values implying that the post graduate students' compliance in these areas is significantly low. The result also indicates that the mean scores earned by post graduate students on the dimensions of data collection and reporting are significantly higher than the reference mean score of 25.00, and also the respondents' overall mean score of 100.12 was significantly higher than the reference mean score 25.00. Based on the overall results, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The implication of this situation is that post graduate students in University of Calabar significantly exhibit ethical compliance in the area of data collection (X = 26.26), data reporting (X=25.93). Going by the sizes of the t-values, it can be said that graduate students' exhibition of ethical compliance in data analysis (t-value -6.39) was significantly low, along with psychometric properties of instrument (t=-1.26). Based on the overall result however, graduate students' (in University of Calabar) exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting is significantly high.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference between male and female post graduate students in their exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data collection, data analysis and reporting. The independent variable of this hypothesis is sex (categorized into male and female) while the dependent variable is the associated four dimensions of research practices. The statistical analysis employed here is the Analysis of variance (ANOVA). The hypothesis testing was done for each of the four dimensions and the overall ethical compliance of research practices. The group size mean and standard deviation are presented on Tables 2 and the results is presented on Table 3

Table 2: Group Sizes, Means and Standard Deviations of Ethical Compliance Variable based on Post Graduate Students Sex

S/no	Ethical compliance	Sex	N	X	SD
1	Psychometric property instrument	Male	517	22.8549	4.88712
		Female	315	22.3302	4.18203
		Total	832	22.6563	4.63722
2	Data collection	Male	517	21.8298	5.13217
		Female	315	20.7746	4.54454
		Total	832	21.4303	4.94177
3	Data analysis	Male	517	22.5145	4.53606
		Female	315	22.2921	3.93463
		Total	832	22.4303	4.31714
4	Reporting	Male	517	27.2747	6.04489
		Female	315	26.9429	5.16387
		Total	832	27.1490	5.72636
5	Overall ethical compliance in research practice	Male	517	94.4739	11.11348
		Female	315	92.3397	9.75507
		Total	832	93.6659	10.66406

Table 3: Analysis of variance of the difference in ethical compliance variable based on faculties

S/No	ethical compliance in research practice	Sources of variance	SS	Df	Ms	f-ratio	Sig
1	Psychometric properties of instrument	Between Groups	53.904	1	53.904	2.51 1	.113
		Within Groups	17815.783	830	21.465		
		Total	17869.687	831			
2	Data collection	Between Groups	217.939	1	217.939	9.01 0	.003
		Within Groups	20076.018	830	24.188		
		Total	20293.957	831			
	Data analysis	Between Groups	9.685	1	9.685	.519	.471
		Within Groups	15478.271	830	18.649		
		Total	15487.957	831			
4	Reporting	Between Groups	21.550	1	21.550	.657	.418
		Within Groups	27227.969	830	32.805		
		Total	27249.519	831			
5	Overall ethical compliance in research practice	Between Groups	891.559	1	891.559	7.90 5	.005
		Within Groups	93611.551	830	112.785		
		Total	94503.111	831			

Not significant at $p < .05$, $df = 5$ and 577 . Critical F-ratio = 3.85

Result of the analysis shown in Table 3 indicates that the F-ratio for the three dimensions in ethical compliance of psychometric properties of instruments, data analysis and reporting in research practice ($F = 2.511$, $F = .519$ and $F = .657$) were each less than the critical F-ratio of 3.85 at 0.05 level of significance with 1 and 830 degree of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference between male and female post graduate students in their exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data analysis and reporting. While the F-ratio for data collection and overall ethical compliance in research practice $F = 9.01$ and $F = 7.905$ were each greater than the critical F-ratio of 3.85 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there is a significant difference between male and female post graduate students in their exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of data collection and overall ethical compliance in research practice

Hypothesis three

There is no significant difference among post graduate students in different faculties in their exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data collection, data analysis and reporting. The independent variable in this hypothesis is post graduate students in various faculties (categorized into 6) while the dependent variable is the four dimensions of exhibition of ethical compliance (in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data collection, data analysis and reporting). The statistical analysis technique adopted to test this hypothesis was multiple Analysis of Variance (MANOVA). The hypothesis tested was done on each of the four dimensions of exhibition of ethical compliance and on the overall component. The group size mean and standard deviation are presented on Tables 4 and The result of the MANOVA is presented on Table 5.

Table 4: Group Sizes, Means and Standard Deviations of Ethical Compliance Variable based on Post Graduate Students' Faculties

s/no	Ethical compliance in	Faculty	N	X	SD
1	Psychometric properties of instruments	Education	171	25.56	7.15
		Social sciences	156	24.82	7.83
		Management sciences	138	24.39	8.15
		Arts	146	23.33	7.57
		Sciences	128	23.87	7.62
		Allied medical sciences	93	26.37	7.13
		Total	832	24.67	7.63
		Total	832	26.12	7.12
2	Data collection	Education	171	26.25	6.83
		Social sciences	156	27.68	7.12
		Management sciences	138	27.68	7.12
		Arts	146	25.74	7.33
		Sciences	128	26.61	6.90
		Allied medical sciences	93	24.77	8.25
		Total	832	26.26	7.23
		Total	832	26.26	7.23

3	Data analysis	Education	171	23.78	7.41
		Social sciences	156	23.48	8.06
		Management science	138	23.36	7.50
		Arts	146	22.38	7.74
		Sciences	128	21.86	7.81
		Allied medical	93	25.15	8.48
		Total	832	23.27	7.83
		4	Reporting	Education	171
Social sciences	156			25.89	7.10
Management sciences	138			26.88	6.57
Arts	146			25.10	7.39
Sciences	128			26.16	7.79
Allied medical	93			26.54	7.27
Total	832			25.85	7.24
5	Overall ethical compliance in research practice			Education	171
		Social sciences	156	100.44	18.80
		Management sciences	138	102.32	18.09
		Arts	146	96.55	18.81
		Sciences	128	98.50	17.92
		Allied medical	93	102.84	19.787
		Total	832	100.12	18.94

Table 4: Multiple Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) of Ethical Compliance Variable based on Post Graduate Students' Faculties

Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig	
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.989	18542.261 ^b	4.000	823.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.011	18542.261 ^b	4.000	823.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	90.120	18542.261 ^b	4.000	823.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	90.120	18542.261 ^b	4.000	823.000	.000
	Pillar's Trace	.018	.749	20.000	3304.000	.777
	Wilks' Lambda	.982	.748	20.000	2730.532	.778
Faculty	Hotelling's Trace	.018	.747	20.000	3286.000	.779
	Roy's Largest Root	.011	1.887 ^c	5.000	826.000	.094

Not significant at $p < .05$, $H_0 = 4$. Critical F-ratio = 3.85

From the mean, the faculty that complied most is Allied Medical ($X=102.84$), followed by Management Science ($X=102.32$), Education ($X=100.85$), Social Science ($X=100.44$) Sciences $X=98.50$ and the least was Arts ($X=96.55$). Result of the analysis shown in Table 4 indicates that the F-ratio pillar analysis ($4.000, 823.000 = 18542.261$: $p < .05$) is significant. This implies that post graduate students in various faculties in University of Calabar differ significantly in the overall exhibition of ethical compliance in psychometric properties of instruments and data analysis, data collection, data analysis, reporting and Overall ethical compliance in research practice.

Discussion

The result of hypothesis one showed that post graduate students of University of Calabar exhibit ethical compliance generally in research practice. Going by the mean scores on Table 1, data collection was observed to have the highest mean (26.26) followed by reporting (25.93). This suggests that the post graduate students considered these two dimensions of exhibition of ethical compliance in research practice to be the ones most practiced. The university post graduate students under study were also rated on the exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments ($X = 24.66$) and data analysis ($X=23.26$) compared to expected mean performance score of 25.00 (see Table 1). This implies that the extent to which students consider and responsibly adhere to the ethics laid down for the use of these practices in research is not significantly high. This finding is in agreement with Ali (2009) and Idika (2016) who indicated in their studies that the skill of instrument construction and determination of psychometric properties are yet to be applied appropriately and efficiently in research practice. The students' relatively poor compliance in research ethics as concerns data analysis as revealed by the low mean value ($x=23.26$) is not surprising as a good number of studies, Duze (2005), Yee and Sam (2012), Bakare and Bakare (2014), Ojating and Uyanah (2015), Eluwa and Eba (2015), confirmed statistical disconnection and sharp practices among students and recommended that equipping researchers with adequate knowledge and orientation will help them avoid spurious research from shut cuts and follow thorough well-defined and rigorous steps of research to arrive at good results.

In summary, the outcome of the overall analysis of exhibition of ethical compliance in research practice of post graduate students shows a t-value of 2.50. This is higher than the critical t-value of 1.96, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis that the university of Calabar post graduate students significantly exhibit ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instrument, data collection, data analysis and reporting is not significantly high. It may therefore, be concluded that post graduate students in university of Calabar exhibit ethical compliance in research practice. The need for a more honest and high quality researches expected to transform lives and institutions as well as society makes it imperative to involve them in ethical committees and other activities to the extent that they see themselves as responsible custodians and producers of rules and regulations which govern research conducts. This further receives the recommendation of Amadi (2015) that increased re-orientation through training of students at seminars and workshops could serve as a means of fostering the development and maintenance of the right conduct in research.

The result of hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant difference between male and female post graduate students in their exhibition of ethical compliance

in terms of psychometric properties of instruments, data collection, data analysis and reporting. It was further revealed that male students showed greater commitment to ethical compliance than their female counterparts. This is in line with the studies of Amadi; Ojini (2015) and Bassey et al (2007) who revealed that there is a small number of female students exhibiting high research commitment in the faculties especially science based disciplines. This implies that most male researchers demonstrate more independence in the use of internet technologies for research than females.

The result of hypothesis three revealed that the university faculties do not differ in the exhibition of ethical compliance in terms of psychometric properties of instruments and data analysis when put together. From the analysis, post graduate students are more compliant in psychometric property of instruments (F-ratio=2.65 than data analysis (F-ratio=2.48), data collection (f-ration =2.09) and reporting (f-ratio = 1.20). This finding agrees partly with Ali (2009) who found discipline influence on instrument psychometric properties' compliance, data collection and analysis to be significantly high, with Education taking the lead and Management Science as the least; but found reporting as the only activity that was not influenced by discipline. This view on reporting in relation to Management Science is a contradiction which future studies need to focus in order to help foster ethical compliance in the research works of this area with the same magnitude of attention as given to other areas of specialization already open for a re-orientation in their research practice. Based on the result, it was found that faculty of Management science and Allied Medical sciences showed the greatest ethical concern in terms of reporting ($x=26.88$); data collection ($x=25.15$) for Management Science and for Allied Medical Sciences, exhibited research ethics most in areas that posed a general challenge to all other faculties. It is therefore, an indication that students in these faculties in their research practices are ethical compliant. Worth mentioning too, is that the University of Calabar has the turnitin softway, hence, the institution is now positioned to checkmate research fraud and improve originality of students' research work. These are some facilities that were met on ground in course of the exploratory interview as to the state of the research services offered to improve graduate research by University of Calabar Graduate School and the Directorate of Research/Quality Assurance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

It was found that post graduate students in University of Calabar have not shown much ethical compliance in their research practice especially in terms of psychometric properties of instruments and data analysis. Their exhibition of ethical compliance in data collection, reporting and the overall was however, significantly high.

The findings also showed significant difference in the ethical compliance of male and female students. The result indicated that the female students were less committed than their male counterparts in their display of research ethics. It was found too, that the post graduate students of different faculties differed significantly in exhibition of ethical compliance with respect to determining psychometric properties of instruments and data analysis while significant difference did not exist among them in the area of data collection and reporting. The mean values showed that Allied Medical Sciences showed higher ethical compliance in their research practice, while faculty of Arts indicated the least commitment to ethical compliance on research practice. From the foregoing, it is

evident that orientation of post graduate students in the Universities towards embracing the ethics of research will help to play down on the so much talked about ethical issues and promote honesty and originality in their research work.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings and conclusion of the study:

1. To prepare the post graduate students for integrity in research, there is need for a re-orientation through increased seminars and workshops at the department and faculty levels as well as institutional level.
2. All Universities should make it a policy to subscribe to anti-plagiarism software like Turnitin, which is already in place in some universities as means of checkmating research fraud, and fostering originality in students' research works.
3. Sanctions against non-compliance should be punitive enough to serve as deterrent.

References

- Ali, H. O. (2009). Evaluation of research skills application among post graduate students in university in south-south, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D dissertation, faculty of education. University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria.
- Amadi, D. O. (2015). Researchers' characteristics and use of multiliteracy platforms for research among post graduate students in universities in south-south, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Dissertation, Faculty of Education, University of Calabar.
- Asim, A. E. & Eni, I. E. (2015). Evaluation of the use and misuse of statistical techniques in educational research in University of Calabar. *Nigerian Journal of Education Research and Evaluation*, 14(1), 183-195.
- Asim, A. E., Kalu, I. M. & Ekwueme, C. O. (2007). Skills in unpublished graduate theses and published researches in science education. *The International Journal Series on Tropical Issues*, 8(1), 89-94.
- Bakare, B. M. & Bakare, O. V. (2014). Statistical concerns in research, assessment and evaluation: The pros and cons. A paper presented at the 16th Annual Conference of Association of Educational Researchers and Evaluators of Nigeria, held in Calabar, 14th – 18th July.
- Bassey, U., Akuegwu, B., Udida, L. & Udey, F (2007). Academic staff research productivity: a study of universities in South-South Zone of Nigeria. *Educational Research and Review*, 2(5), 103-108.
- Bisong, F. E. (2012). Graduate School Deanship Election: an agenda for continuing consolidation and transformation.

- Chen, J.F. (2008). "Gender differences in Taiwan business writing errors". Retrieved June 10, 2008, from <http://occor.edu/tw>.
- Cohen, L. Manor, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research methods in education*. New York: Routledge.
- Duze, C. O. (2010). An analysis of problem encountered by post – post graduate students in Nigeria universities. *Journal of Social Science*, 22(2), 129 – 137.
- Eluwa, I.O. &Eba, M.A. (2015). Undergraduate students' disconnections in statistics: Implications for assessment reforms. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 14(3), 20-32.
- Eze, E. A. (2011). Assessment of research skills of students in Cross River State Health Training Institutions. Unpublished Master's thesis, Faculty of Education, University of Calabar.
- Idika, D. O. (2016). Assessment of research skills and practices among academic staff in Akwa Ibom and Cross River state, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D dissertation Faculty of Education, University of Calabar.
- Idika, D. O., Joshua M. T & Umoinyang, I. E. (2017). Assessment of research skills among academic staff in public universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River states, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 16(2), 119 - 135.
- Isangedighi, A. J. (2012). Educational research in context. In A. J. Isangedighi (Eds.), *Essentials of Research and Statistics in Education and Social Sciences* (pp. 18-20). Calabar: Eti-nwa Associates.
- Joshua, M. T. (2005). *Fundamentals of tests and measurement in education*. Calabar – Nigeria: The University of Calabar Press.
- Joshua, M. T., Nwogwugwu, C. E., & Ikirima, B. (2015). Skills possessed in information and communication technology (ICT) in data analysis: A case of Lecturers in universities in Abia State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 14(3), 125-135.
- Nenty, H. J & Umoinyang, I. E. (2004) *Principles of test constitution*. Calabar: Helimo Associates.
- Office of Research Integrity. Guidelines for responsible conducts of research. 132 cathedral Of Learning. 412-624-3007
- Ojating, H. A. & Uyanah, D. A. (2015). Wrong usage of statistical tools in education researches: The way out. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 14(1), 208-225
- Umoinyang, I.E. (2015). Data analysis in educational research. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 14(2), 1-14
- Yee, L. T. & Sam, H. K. (2012). *Elementary statistics for sciences with SPSS*. Malaysia: Sarawak.